

CREW SYSTEM ENGINEERING METHODOLOGY: PROCESS AND DISPLAY REQUIREMENTS

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Abstract

There currently lacks a crew systems engineering approach for integrating the crew station within the total aircraft system. To address this problem, ONT (Code 212) and the Naval Air Systems Command (NAVAIR 531/PMA 202) initiated the Advanced Technology Crew Station (ATCS) program at the Naval Air Development Center (NADC). ATCS involves multiple Navy laboratories, McDonnell Douglas, and Boeing Military Aircraft. One of the products of the ATCS program is a crew systems engineering methodology. During implementation of the methodology a major design gap was identified. A method was needed to derive and justify display requirements and display technology options based on the mission, aircraft, and crew system requirements.

This paper discusses the ATCS program, the crew systems engineering methodology and the derivation of display requirements within the methodology.

ATCS Program

Problem

The traditional approach to design, acquisition, and evaluation of an aircraft crew station is now in need of major improvement. Overall operator performance has become a limiting factor in weapon system effectiveness. Problems associated with integrating crew systems technologies with other impacting technologies, as well as related aircraft design tradeoffs, have aggravated the situation further.

(Crew system technologies include human factors, controls and displays, seating and escape systems, head protection, Chemical and Biological protection, laser eye protection, acceleration physiology and environmental protection; impacting technologies include sensors, structures, aerodynamics, signature, computers/software.) Absent or inadequate methods and tools for blending the various technologies have not fully optimized the effectiveness and survivability of the human operator in Naval aircraft. In addition, the knowledge of how to utilize crew system methods, tools, and data in supporting Navy and industry aircraft development activities is very limited.

Objective

The Navy's Advanced Technology Crew Station program was established to develop, demonstrate, and validate a crew systems engineering method that will achieve effective integration of aircrew and technologies within the aircraft system. To validate the crew systems engineering method, several integrated crew station concepts for next generation advanced tactical aircraft will be developed and evaluated. Final ATCS program products will be 1) a validated crew systems engineering method for use by DoD and airframe industry for designing effective, integrated crew systems, 2) tools for definition and evaluation of crew system performance requirements, 3) modification of relevant aircraft weapon system specifications (e.g., SD-24) to include crew systems performance requirements, and 4) advanced crew station concepts for Navy's next generation tactical aircraft.

Methodology

The aircrew-centered crew systems engineering methodology approaches the aircraft design from the aircrews' perspective. There are three important features of the methodology. First, it prescribes an iterative process of design activities and events aimed at identifying and maintaining focus on the critical crew station issues during crew station design. Second, it provides a common framework for the timely and cost effective use of various computer-based development tools for addressing and resolving crew station issues. A series of computer-based tools can allow for more precise quantitative information about the impact of crew station compromises on the human and ultimately on mission performance, and can substantially reduce the delay in availability of that information in the design process. Third, the methodology explicitly promotes multi-disciplinary inputs to the crew station design. By requiring interchange of design information through interdisciplinary coordination, it fosters the earliest possible identification and resolution of issues that might unnecessarily constrain the crew station design.

The core structure of the crew systems engineering methodology is illustrated in Figure 1. The first five steps define activities required to translate operational requirements into crew system requirements. Included in the requirements definition is an iterative process of man/machine function allocation. In the next step, the crew system requirements are used to postulate crew system concepts. In configuration development (blocks 8 through 18), candidate design configurations are developed and iterations are performed as required to home in on candidate configurations. The final product is an optimized, integrated crew station design. Detailed discussion of each methodology block is provided in reference 1.

One unique aspect of this methodology is that it provides traceability from mission level requirements (block 2) to aircraft level system requirements (block 3) to crew station

requirements (block 5). This requirements traceability is also provided during selection of specific crew station technology options and throughout the iterative crew station configuration development cycle. This traceability is provided within the methodology using a technique called Quality Function Deployment (QFD)².

Figure 1. Crew System Engineering Methodology

QFD Process

The QFD has been successfully used by the Japanese in the automotive industry to

insure that customer requirements were satisfied. Figure 2 illustrates the overall matrix approach of QFD. The QFD begins with the overall requirements (i.e. the What's in the matrix) which in our application is the mission requirements. Each "What" is broken down into one or more "How's" which represent, in our case, aircraft system requirements. The "How Much" is a quantification and/or qualification of the aircraft system requirements. The relationship between each "How" and "What" is rated either weak, medium or strong. The "How" items (i.e. aircraft system requirements) are further broken down by becoming requirements (i.e. "What's") and new "How's" (i.e. Crew Station requirements) are defined to meet the aircraft system requirements. The QFD approach used in generation and linking of the mission requirements, aircraft systems requirements and crew station requirements is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 2. QFD Matrix

During the selection of crew station technology options to meet the information

transfer requirements, there was a problem in selecting specific display options. There was a gap in going from the crew station requirements to defining the display requirements (e.g., the display size) to the selection of specific display technologies. Given the requirements for the crew station, how do you select specific display technology options? Traditionally, the display options have been based on one or two driving requirements such as night vision capability or reduced aircraft signature which usually are incompatible with the majority of the crew station display requirements. What was needed was a method of translating the crew station requirements into relevant display requirements in order to select appropriate display technology options for the crew station. The remainder of this paper will discuss a method for translating crew station requirements into appropriate display requirements.

Figure 3. QFD Requirements Derivation

Display Requirements Application

One of the crew system requirements identified as a result of applying the QFD process was the transfer of information from system to crew. Further analysis was required to define this requirement. The general approach used to derive information requirements is presented followed by a discussion of how the requirements were synthesized into viable display options.

Derivation of Information Requirements

The information requirements³ were derived from three mission scenarios consisting of combat air patrol, deck launched intercept and strike^{4,5}. To facilitate the analysis, the mission scenarios were broken into phases (e.g., take-off, climb, cruise, etc.). The phases were made up of segments or common categories of aircrew tasks which were essentially the same as the system requirements derived in the QFD process (e.g., aviate, navigate, etc.). Each segment was comprised of the tasks needed to perform the segment function. The tasks were analyzed to determine significant aircrew decision points and the corresponding information needed to make those decisions. Figure 4 depicts the general process used to derive the information requirements along with illustrative examples.

MISSION SCENARIO:	STRIKE
PHASE:	ATTACK
SEGMENT:	WEAPON DELIVERY
DECISION TASK:	COMMIT WEAPON
INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS:	DELIVERY MODE SELECTED FLIGHT PATH TO RELEASE AIRSPEED TIME OF FALL : DELIVERY SOLUTION CUEING

Figure 4. Information Requirements Derivation

Synthesis of Requirements

When synthesizing crew system requirements for displays, information was assumed to be transferred from the system to the crew. What needs to be analyzed is what and how information can best be presented to the crew. Initially, the modes of communicating the information to the crew were identified. Information types were then allocated to the modes as shown in Figure 5.

Visual Option. The visual option can be further partitioned into head referenced/eyes-out and fixed-display categories because there

are two distinct types of information. For the head-referenced and eyes-out options, a major interaction with the external environment is required. Information that should be included for these options are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Information Requirements Tree

For the fixed-display option, it is assumed that displays inside the cockpit can be used because the relationship to the environment is not that closely coupled. The types of information that is associated with the fixed display option is shown in Figure 5.

Another analysis was performed to determine the types of information and formats that could be allocated to the visual display surface options as shown in Figure 6. The BVR (Beyond Visual Range) tactical situation requirement would be scalable from 5 to 160 nautical miles, have a map format with symbology, and overlays consisting of items such as a navigation plan and weapon employment information. This could be implemented via a large, fixed panel of approximately 400 square inches or a virtual presentation via a virtual vision system. Gene Adam's "Big Picture" is an example of a large, fixed panel and is undergoing evaluation in McDonnell Aircraft's domed simulator.

For the WVR (Within Visual Range) tactical situation requirement, it is envisioned that a perspective scene with terrain and zoom capability would be provided. The format

DISPLAY RGT	FORMAT	OVERLAY	SURFACE TYPE					
			HEAD REFERENCED EYES OUT (SPHERICAL)	FIXED (400 in2 min)	WINDOW (W/ CURSOR CONTROL)			
					20 in2	30 in2	40 in2	
BVR TACTICAL SITUATION SCALABLE 5-160 NM	MAP W/ SYMB	NAV PLAN WPN EMP TARGETING		X				
WVR TACTICAL SITUATION PERSPECT SCENE/TERRAIN W/ ZOOM	3D VIRTUAL AND/OR SYMB	NAVEXEC WPN EMP TARGETING	X					
PRIMARY FLIGHT	VARIOUS		X					
BACKUP FLIGHT INFO	VARIOUS					IF PRIM FAIL		
SYSTEM STATUS	VARIOUS					9/2*		
WEAPON STATUS	VARIOUS						1/1*	
SENSOR DISPLAY	RDR/IR/EO							5/3*
MENU	VARIOUS						1/1*	

- TOTAL/SIMULTANEOUS

Figure 6. Display Requirements Allocation Matrix

would consist of 3D virtual and/or symbology with overlays identical to those of the BVR requirement. This would be implemented via a spherical head referenced/eyes out configuration which would also include primary flight information.

Since the large fixed display will occupy most of the available display area, windows are being considered as replacements for dedicated status type displays. They would be integrated with larger display surfaces and selectable via a menu. As shown in Figure 6, windows would be used for such items as backup flight information, system status, weapon status, sensor displays, and menus. Depending on the application it is estimated that the window sizes required would include 20, 30, and 40 square inch varieties. In addition, not all windows would be displayed simultaneously. The entries in Figure 6 provide an estimate of the total number of windows required for each display requirement

and the number of windows that would be displayed simultaneously.

Auditory Option. Auditory options were provided to duplicate certain warning type information to more readily attract the pilot's attention. Candidate auditory information types are shown in Figure 5.

Tactile Option. The tactile option can be used to acknowledge system responses resulting from control actions as well as backup for critical warnings. This is most applicable when virtual control is implemented. The warning capability is most attractive for high activity periods to get the pilot's attention when other mediums are not available.

Crew System Display Requirements

Using the mission requirements flow down in conjunction with the above display

analyses enabled the identification and synthesis of comprehensive crew system requirements for the transfer of information from the system to the crew. The crew system visual information requirements are expressed in terms of head referenced, fixed, heads up, and always in view categories. The auditory requirements are subdivided into voice and tone categories. In addition, the tactile requirement is specified.

Candidate display technology options were then identified and evaluated for each crew system requirement using the QFD process. Some of the visual display system options include a heads-up display, dome surface, large panel with windows, and abutted panels. The auditory options include a voice and tone generator and the tactile option consists of a tactile sleeve.

Summary/Future Work

This paper provided an overview of the ATCS methodology, QFD process, and an approach used to derive display requirements. The ATCS program recently completed a preliminary design phase consisting of deriving crew system requirements, developing system concepts and technology options, and performing QFD trade studies to identify candidate technology options. This includes up to block 8 of the methodology in Figure 1. Future efforts will include design trade studies and integration tasks necessary to produce CAD configurations and static mockups.

There are a number of lessons learned from the ATCS effort. First, advanced aircraft/crew system concepts must be postulated to stimulate creative thinking prior to the selection of crew station technology options. Second, mission requirements must be expressed in terms which are meaningful to crew system requirements and traceable from the highest level through the resultant design. Lastly, an effective methodology must be employed which relates crew system requirements to technology options, enables visibility of design trades, provides team interaction, and facilitates the integration of

technologies into a synergistic crew system. It is felt that the ATCS methodology, which includes the QFD process, is a major step in producing an effective, integrated crew system.

References

1. "Preliminary Human-Centered Crew Station Design Methodology", Air Vehicle and Crew Systems Technology Dept., Naval Air Development Center, September, 1990.
2. Eureka, W. E. and Ryan, N. E., "The Customer-Driven Company: Managerial Perspectives on QFD", ASI Press, 1988.
3. "ATCS Mission Timelines", Veda Report 33236-90U/P3838, 2 February 1990.
4. Cohen, D., "Identification of Advanced Technology Crew Station Decision Points and Information Requirements", Air Vehicle and Crew Systems Technology Dept., Naval Air Development Center, January 1990.
5. Hodorovich, N. and Cohen, D., "Year 2005 Mission Scenarios for Advanced Technology Crew Stations (Secret)", Naval Air Development Center, November 21, 1989.